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Perilous brilliant blue G remediation by the help of crosslinked hydrogels

Dhanya K.R^{1*}, Gigimol M.G²

¹CIPET-IPT, Udyogamandal, Kochi, Kerala, India

²Alphonsa College, Pala, Kerala, India

*Corresponding author: Dhanya K. R (k_r_dhanya@yahoo.co.in)

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Introduction: The harmful natures of textile effluents are of great concern (1-2). The study focused on Brilliant Blue G and is lethal to mankind. Several health risks were generally found in aquatic as well as humans. The necessity of remediation is vital (3). Tetraethyleneglycol diacrylate (TTEGDA) cross-linked hydrogel was prepared by suspension polymerization and used for the complete exclusion of contaminated effluents. Binding studies were carried out for the exclusion of these contaminated substances. Effect of concentration, amounts of polymer added, nature and degree of crosslinking, effect of temperature etc were analyzed and characterizations were analyzed using SEM, UV-VIS, FTIR etc. The entire study gives a clear picture for the removal of toxic effluents from water.

Methods: The TTEGDA-crosslinked hydrogels were synthesised by suspension polymerisation method. Acrylic acid and N-vinyl pyrrolidone are the copolymers used. Binding studies were followed such as effects of concentration, amounts of polymer added, effects of temperature and nature and degree of crosslinking etc. Characterization techniques such as FTIR, UV-VIS and SEM were analysed.

Results & Discussions: The greatly enhanced adsorption capacity of crosslinked hydrogel was successfully achieved by batch equilibration method. Characterization techniques give evidence to the dye binding. Varying experimental conditions were applied for these studies. The perilous dye Brilliant Blue G was eliminated from water by the help of hydrogels. The greater ability of hydrogel was experimentally detected.

Conclusions: Toxic textile effluents containing Brilliant Blue G were removed by using efficient adsorbent, TTEGDA-crosslinked acrylic acid and N-vinyl pyrrolidone. Several experimental conditions were followed and from the results Brilliant Blue G was effectively expelled from water and the higher uptake capacity of adsorbent was effectively detected.

Key words: *Crosslinked hydrogel, Brilliant blue G, Waste-water remediation, Water pollution*

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